

Anti-fuzzy Ideals of BZ-algebra

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce the notion of anti-fuzzy Ideals in BZ-algebra, several appropriate examples are provided and some properties are investigated. The image and the inverse image of anti-fuzzy ideals in BZ-algebra are defined and how the image and the inverse image of anti-fuzzy ideals in BZ-algebra become anti-fuzzy ideals are studied. Moreover, the cartesian product of anti-fuzzy ideals are given.

Keywords

BZ-algebras, fuzzy ideal, anti-fuzzy subalgebra, anti-fuzzy ideal, image and pre-image of anti-fuzzy ideals, Cartesian product.

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INTRODUCTION

BCK-algebras form an important class of logical algebras introduced by K. Iseki [13] and was extensively investigated by several researchers. The class of all BCK-algebras is quasi variety. J. Meng and Y. B. Jun posed an interesting problem (solved in [16]) whether the class of all BCK-algebras is a variety. In connection with this problem, Komori introduced in [15] a notion of BCC algebras. W.A. Dudek (cf. [4]) redefined the notion of BCC-algebras by using a dual form of the ordinary definition in the sense of Y. Komori and studied ideals and congruences of BCC-algebras. In [20,21], C. Prabpayak and U. Leerawat introduced a new algebraic structure, which is called KU-algebra. They gave the concept of homomorphisms of KU-algebras and investigated some related properties. L.A. Zadeh [23] introduced the notion of fuzzy subsets. At present this concept has been applied to many mathematical branches, such as group, functional analysis, probability theory, topology, and so on. In 1991, O.G. Xi [22] applied this concept to BCK-algebras, and he introduced the notion of fuzzy sub-algebras (ideals) of the BCK-algebras with respect to minimum, and since then Jun et al studied fuzzy ideals (cf. [14]), and moreover several fuzzy structures in BCC-algebras are considered (cf. [17]). In [6], the anti-fuzzy AB-ideals of AB-algebras and in [11], the anti-fuzzy AT-ideals of AT-algebras were introduced. Several theorems are stated and proved. Omar in [18] and Patthanankoor in [19] have introduced the notion of BZ-algebras, ideals, subalgebras and studied the relations among them and gave the concept of homomorphism of BZ-algebras and investigated some related properties. Abed in [1-3], studied the structure of BZ -algebras and its properties, studied the isomorphism of BZ-algebras and

introduced on the special ideals in BZ -algebras. Ghabue and Hameed in [5], studied the fuzzy algebraic structures was started with the introduction of the concept of fuzzy ideals of BZ -algebras and investigated several basic properties which are related to fuzzy ideals. They described how to deal with the homomorphism of image and inverse image of fuzzy ideals. And they have also proved that the Cartesian product of fuzzy ideals is a fuzzy ideal. In this paper, we introduce the notion of anti-fuzzy ideals of BZ -algebras and then we study the homomorphism image and inverse image of anti-fuzzy ideals. We also prove that the Cartesian product of anti-fuzzy ideals are anti-fuzzy ideals.

2. Preliminaries

In this section we introduced an algebraic structure called a BZ -algebra

Definition 2.1([18,19]). Let $(X;*,0)$ be an algebra with operation $(+)$ and constant (0) . X is called a BZ -algebra if it satisfies the following identities: for any $x,y,z \in X$,

$$(BZ-1) ((x * z) * (y * z)) * (x * y) = 0;$$

$$(BZ-2) x * 0 = x;$$

$$(BZ-3) x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x = 0 \text{ implies that } x = y.$$

Remark 2.2. ([18,19]).

On BZ -algebra $(X,*,0)$, we defined a binary relation \leq on X by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 2.3 ([1-3,18,19]). Let $(X;*,0)$ be a BZ -algebra, then (X, \leq) is a partially ordered set. It is easy to show that the following properties are true for a BZ -algebra. For any $x,y,z \in X$:

$$(P-1) x * ((x * y) * y) = 0;$$

$$(P-2) x * x = 0;$$

$$(P-3) x * (y * z) = y * (x * z);$$

$$(P-4) ((x * y) * y) * y = x * y;$$

$$(P-5) (x * y) * 0 = (x * 0) * (y * 0);$$

$$(P-6) (x * y) * ((z * x) * (z * y)) = 0;$$

$$(P-7) x \leq y \text{ implies } y * z \leq x * z;$$

$$(P-8) x \leq y \text{ implies } z * x \leq z * y.$$

Definition 2.4. ([19]). A subset S of a BZ -algebra X is called **subalgebra of X** if $x * y \in S$ whenever $x,y \in S$.

Definition 2.5. ([1-3]). A non-empty subset I of a BZ -algebra $(X,*,0)$ is called **ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for any $x,y,z \in X$

$$(I-1) 0 \in I$$

$$(I-2) x * y \in I \text{ and } x \in I \text{ imply } y \in I.$$

Definition 2.6. ([7]). Let I be an ideal of BZ -algebra $(X,*,0)$. Define **the relation \sim on X** by $x \sim y$ if and only if $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$. Then the relation \sim is an equivalence relation on X and $[0]_I = \{x \in X \mid x \sim 0\}$ is an ideal of X .

Remark 2.7 ([7]). Let \sim be an equivalence relation on a BZ -algebra $(X,*,0)$ and I be an ideal of X . Define $[x]_I$ by $[x]_I = \{y \in X \mid x \sim y\} = \{y \in X \mid x * y \in I, y * x \in I\}$, then the family $\{[x]_I \mid x \in X\}$ gives a partition of X which is denoted by X/I .

For any $x,y \in X$, we defined $[x]_I \circ [y]_I = [x * y]_I$, then the binary operation \circ is a mapping from $X/I \times X/I$ to X/I .

It is easily checked that $(X/I, \circ, [0]_I)$ is a BZ -algebra.

Moreover, the set X/I is called **the quotient BZ -algebra**. And if I is an ideal of BZ -algebra X , then it is clear that $[a]_I = I$, for all a in I .

Proposition 2.8 ([18,19]). Every ideal of BZ -algebra $(X,*,0)$ is a subalgebra of X .

Proposition 2.9 ([18,19]). Let $\{I_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ideals of BZ -algebra $(X,*,0)$. The intersection of any set of BZ -ideals of X is also an ideal of X .

Definition 2.10 ([10]). Let $(X,*,0)$ and $(Y;*',0')$ be nonempty sets. The mapping $f : (X;*,0) \rightarrow (Y;*',0')$ is called a **homomorphism** if it satisfies: $f(x * y) = f(x) *' f(y)$, for all $x,y \in X$. The set $\{x \in X \mid f(x) = 0'\}$ is called **the kernel of f** denoted by $\ker f$.

Theorem 2.11 ([1-3]). Let $f : (X;*,0) \rightarrow (Y;*',0')$ be a homomorphism of a BZ -algebra X into an BZ -algebra Y , then:

$$(1) f(0) = 0'.$$

$$(2) f \text{ is injective if and only if } \ker f = \{0\}.$$

$$(3) x \leq y \text{ implies } f(x) \leq f(y).$$

Theorem 2.12 ([1-3]). Let $f : (X;*,0) \rightarrow (Y;*',0')$ be a homomorphism of an BZ -algebra X into an BZ -algebra Y , then:

$$(F_1) \text{ If } S \text{ is a subalgebra of } X, \text{ then } f(S) \text{ is a subalgebra of } Y, \text{ where } f \text{ is onto.}$$

$$(F_2) \text{ If } I \text{ is ideal of } X, \text{ then } f(I) \text{ is ideal in } Y, \text{ where } f \text{ is onto.}$$

$$(F_3) \text{ If } D \text{ is a subalgebra of } Y, \text{ then } f^{-1}(D) \text{ is a subalgebra of } X.$$

$$(F_4) \text{ If } J \text{ is ideal in } Y, \text{ then } f^{-1}(J) \text{ is ideal in } X.$$

$$(F_5) \ker f \text{ is ideal of } X.$$

$$(F_6) \text{ Im}(f) \text{ is a subalgebra of } Y.$$

Definition 2.13 ([23]). Let $(X, *, 0)$ be a nonempty set, a fuzzy subset μ of X is a mapping $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$.

Definition 2.14. [23]. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of a set X . For $t \in [0, 1]$, the set $\mu_t = U(\mu, t) = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \geq t\}$, is called upper level cut (level subset) of μ and the set $L(\mu, t) = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \leq t\}$ is called lower level cut of μ .

Definition 2.15 ([9]).

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a mapping nonempty sets X and Y respectively. If μ is a fuzzy subset of X , then the fuzzy subset β of Y defined by:

$$f(\mu)(y) = \begin{cases} \sup\{\mu(x): x \in f^{-1}(y)\} & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) = \{x \in X, f(x) = y\} \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

is said to be the image of μ under f .

Similarly if β is a fuzzy subset of Y , then the fuzzy subset $\mu = (\beta \circ f)$ of X (i.e the fuzzy subset defined by $\mu(x) = \beta(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$) is called the pre-image of β under f .

Definition 2.16 ([9]).

A fuzzy subset μ of a set X **has sup property** if for any subset T of X , there exist $t_0 \in T$ such that $\mu(t_0) = \sup\{\mu(t) \mid t \in T\}$.

Definition 2.17([1,18]). Let $(X, *, 0)$ be an BZ-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy subalgebra of X** if for all $x, y \in X$,

$$\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}.$$

Proposition 2.18([1,19]). Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BZ-algebra

$(X, *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X , then for any $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is a subalgebra of X .

Definition 2.19. [5]. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an BZ-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y \in X$,

(1) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.

(2) $\mu(y) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(x)\}$.

Proposition 2.20[5]. Every fuzzy Ideal of BZ-algebra is fuzzy subalgebra.

Proposition 2.23 ([5]). Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism between BZ-algebras X and Y respectively.

- 1- For every fuzzy subalgebra β of Y , $f^{-1}(\beta)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .
- 2- For every fuzzy subalgebra μ of X , $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of Y , where f is onto.
- 3- For every fuzzy Ideal β of Y , $f^{-1}(\beta)$ is a fuzzy ideal of X .
- 4- For every fuzzy Ideal μ of X with sup property, $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y , where f is onto.

3. Anti-fuzzy subalgebras and Homomorphism of BZ-algebras

In this section, we will introduce a new notion called a anti-fuzzy subalgebra

Definition 3.1.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an BZ-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ of X is called an **anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X** if for all $x, y \in X$,

$$\mu(x * y) \leq \max\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}.$$

Example 3.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BZ-algebra. It is easy to show that $I = \{0, 1\}$ is an subalgebra of X .

Define a fuzzy subset $v: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by, $v(x) = \begin{cases} 0.2 & x \in \{0,1\} \\ 0.4 & x \in \{2,3\} \end{cases}$

Then μ is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Routine calculation gives that μ is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of BZ-algebras X .

Proposition 3.3.

Let μ be an anti-fuzzy subset of an BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X , then it satisfies: for any $t \in [0, 1]$, $L(\mu, t) \neq \emptyset$ implies $L(\mu, t)$ is a subalgebra of X .

Proof:

Assume that μ is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X , let $t \in [0,1]$ be such that $L(\mu, t) \neq \emptyset$, and let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x, y \in L(\mu, t)$, then

$\mu(x) \leq t$ and $\mu(y) \leq t$, so $\mu(x * y) \leq \max\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} \leq t$, so that $(x * y) \in L(\mu, t)$. Hence $L(\mu, t)$ is a subalgebra of X . ■

Proposition 3.4.

Let μ be an anti-fuzzy subset of an BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If $U(\mu, t)$ is a subalgebra of X , for all $t \in [0, 1]$, $L(\mu, t) \neq \emptyset$, then μ is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof:

Suppose that μ is not anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X , satisfies $L(\mu, t)$ is a subalgebra of X . Now, assume $\mu(x * y) > \max\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$,

taking $t_0 = \frac{1}{2}(\mu(x * y) + \max\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\})$, we have $t_0 \in [0, 1]$ and

$\max\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} < t_0 < \mu(x * y)$, it follows that $x, y \in L(\mu, t_0)$ and

$x * y \notin L(\mu, t_0)$, this is a contradiction since $L(\mu, t_0)$ is a subalgebra of X , therefore μ is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X . ■

Corollary 3.5.

If a fuzzy subset μ of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra, then for every $t \in Im(\mu)$, $L(\mu, t)$ is a subalgebra of X .

Corollary 3.6.

Let I be a subalgebra of an BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then for any fixed number t in an open interval $(0,1)$, there exist an anti-fuzzy subalgebra μ of X such that $L(\mu, t)=I$.

Proof:

Define $\mu: X \rightarrow [0: 1]$ by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \in I \\ t & \text{if } x \notin I \end{cases}$. Where t is a fixed number in $(0,1)$.

Clearly, $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$ and we have level sets $L(\mu, 0) = I$ or $L(\mu, t) = X$, which are subalgebras of X , then from Proposition (3.4), μ is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X . ■

Proposition 3.7.

The union of any set of anti-fuzzy subalgebras of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is also anti-fuzzy subalgebra.

Proof:

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of anti-fuzzy subalgebras of BZ-algebra X , then for any $x, y \in X, i \in \Lambda$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y) &= \sup(\mu_i(x * y)) \leq \sup\{\max\{\mu_i(x), \mu_i(y)\}\} \\ &\leq \max\{\sup(\mu_i(x)), \sup(\mu_i(y))\} \\ &= \max\{(\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y), (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x)\}. \quad \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Remark 3.8.

The intersection of any set of anti-fuzzy subalgebras of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is not necessarily anti-fuzzy subalgebra as the example.

Example 3.9.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BZ-algebra. It is easy to show that $I = \{0, 2\}$ and $J = \{0, 3\}$ are subalgebras of X . Define a fuzzy subset $\mu, \nu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.2 & x \in \{0,2\} \\ 0.7 & x \in \{3,1\} \end{cases} \text{ and } \nu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.3 & x \in \{0,3\} \\ 0.8 & x = 1 \\ 0.9 & x = 2 \end{cases}. \text{ Then } \mu \text{ and } \nu \text{ are anti-fuzzy subalgebras of } X.$$

$$\text{But } \mu \cap \nu(x) = \min\{\mu(x), \nu(x)\} = \begin{cases} 0.2 & x \in \{0,2\} \\ 0.7 & x = 1 \\ 0.3 & x = 3 \end{cases}$$

is not anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X , since $x = 2, y = 3$,

$$\mu \cap \nu(2 * 3) = 0.7 \not\leq \max\{\mu \cap \nu(2), \mu \cap \nu(3)\} = 0.3$$

Proposition 3.10.

The intersection of any set of anti-fuzzy subalgebras of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is also anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X where is chain (Artinian).

Proof:

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of anti-fuzzy subalgebras of BZ-algebra X , then for any $x, y \in X, i \in \Lambda$,

$$\begin{aligned}
(\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y) &= \inf_{i \in \Lambda} (\mu_i(x * y)) \leq \inf_{i \in \Lambda} \{\max\{\mu_i(x), \mu_i(y)\}\} \\
&\leq \max\{\inf_{i \in \Lambda} (\mu_i(x)), \inf_{i \in \Lambda} (\mu_i(y))\} \\
&= \max\{(\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y), (\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x)\}. \blacksquare
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.11.

A homomorphic pre-image of anti-fuzzy subalgebra is also an anti-fuzzy subalgebra.

Proof:

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0)$ be a homomorphism of BZ-algebras, β is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of Y and μ the pre-image of β under f , let $x, y \in X$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu(x * y) &= \beta(f(x * y)) = \beta(f(x) * f(y)) \\
&\leq \max\{\beta(f(x)), \beta(f(y))\} \\
&= \max\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}. \blacksquare
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.12.

An anti-fuzzy subset μ of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ has inf property if for any subset T of X , there exist $t_0 \in T$ such that $\mu(t_0) = \inf_{t \in T} \mu(t)$.

Theorem 3.13.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0)$ be an epimorphism between BZ-algebras X and Y respectively and f has inf property. For every anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X , $f(\mu)$ is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of Y .

Proof:

By Definition (2.15), $\beta(y') = f(\mu)(y') = \inf_{x \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(x)$, for all $y' \in Y$.

We have to prove that $\beta(x' * y') \leq \max\{\beta(x'), \beta(y')\}$, for all $x', y' \in Y$.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0)$ be an epimorphism of BZ-algebras, μ is a anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X with inf property and β the image of μ under f , since μ is anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X , for any $x', y' \in Y$, let $x_0 \in f^{-1}(x'), y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')$ be such that $\mu(x_0) = \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t)$, $\mu(y_0) = \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(t)$ and $\mu(x_0 * y_0) = \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(x' * y')} \mu(t)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta(x' * y') &= \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(x' * y')} \mu(t) = \mu(x_0 * y_0) \\
&\leq \max\{\mu(x_0), \mu(y_0)\} \\
&= \max\{\inf_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t), \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(t)\} \\
&= \max\{\beta(x'), \beta(y')\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence β is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of Y . \blacksquare

4. Anti-fuzzy Ideals and Homomorphism of BZ-algebras

In this section, we will introduce a new notion called an anti-fuzzy ideal of BZ-algebra and study several basic properties of it.

Definition 4.1.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an BZ-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ of X is called an **anti-fuzzy ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions, for all $x, y \in X$,

- (AFI₁) $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$,
- (AFI₂) $\mu(y) \leq \max\{\mu(x * y), \mu(x)\}$.

Example 4.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BZ-algebra. It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{0, 1\}$ is ideals of X .

Define a fuzzy subset $v: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $v(x) = \begin{cases} 0.2 & x \in \{0, 1\} \\ 0.4 & x \in \{2, 3\} \end{cases}$.

Routine calculation gives that v is an anti-fuzzy ideal of BZ-algebras X .

Lemma 4.3.

Let μ be an anti-fuzzy ideal of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and if $x \leq y$, then $\mu(0 * y) \leq \mu(0 * x)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof:

Assume that $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$, and $\mu(0 * y) \leq \max\{\mu(x * y), \mu(0 * x)\} = \max\{\mu(0), \mu(0 * x)\} = \mu(0 * x)$. Hence $\mu(0 * y) \leq \mu(0 * x)$. \blacksquare

Proposition 4.4.

A fuzzy subset μ of an BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X , then for any $t \in [0, 1]$, $L(\mu, t)$ is an Ideal of X , where $L(\mu, t) \neq \emptyset$.

Proof:

Assume that μ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X , by (AFBZI₁), we have $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$, therefore $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x) \leq t$, for $x \in L(\mu, t)$ and so $0 \in L(\mu, t)$.

Let $x, y \in X$ such that $x * y \in L(\mu, t)$ and $x \in L(\mu, t)$, then $\mu((x * y) * z) \leq t$ and $\mu(x) \leq t$, since μ is an anti-fuzzy Ideal it follows that $\mu(y) \leq \max\{\mu(x * y), \mu(x)\} \leq t$ and that $y \in L(\mu, t)$.

Hence $L(\mu, t)$ is an ideal of X . ■

Proposition 4.5.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of an BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, if $L(\mu, t)$ is an ideal of X , where $L(\mu, t) \neq \emptyset$, for every $t \in [0, 1]$, then μ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof:

Now, we only need to show that (AFI₁) and (AFI₂) are true. If (AFI₁) is false, then there exist $x \in X$ such that $\mu(0) > \mu(x)$.

If we take $t = \frac{1}{2}(\mu(x) + \mu(0))$, then $\mu(0) > t$ and $0 \leq \mu(x) < t \leq 1$ thus $x \in L(\mu, t)$ and $L(\mu, t) \neq \emptyset$.

As $L(\mu, t)$ is an ideal of X , we have $0 \in L(\mu, t)$ and so $\mu(0) \leq t$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (AFI₂) is not true, then there exist $x, y \in X$ such that, $\mu(y) > \max\{\mu(x * y), \mu(x)\}$.

Putting $t = \frac{1}{2}(\mu(y) + \max\{\mu(x * y), \mu(x)\})$, then

$\mu(y) > t$ and $0 \leq \max\{\mu(x * y), \mu(x)\} < t \leq 1$, hence

$\mu(x * y) < t$ and $\mu(x) < t$, imply that $(y) \in L(\mu, t)$, since $L(\mu, t)$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal, it follows that $(y) \in L(\mu, t)$ and that $\mu(y) \leq t$, this is also a contradiction.

Hence μ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Proposition 4.6.

The union of any set of anti-fuzzy ideals of BZ-algebra is also anti-fuzzy ideal.

Proof:

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of anti-fuzzy ideals of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, by (AFI₁), we have $\mu_i(0) \leq \mu_i(x)$ for all $x \in X$, therefore $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i(0) \leq \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i(x)$.

By (AFI₂), for any $x, y \in X$, $i \in \Lambda$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y) &= \sup\{\mu_i(y)\} \\ &\leq \sup\{\max\{\mu_i(x * y), \mu_i(x)\}\} \\ &\leq \max\{\sup\{\mu_i(x * y)\}, \sup\{\mu_i(x)\}\} \\ &= \max\{(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y), (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Remark 4.7.

The intersection of any set of anti-fuzzy ideals of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is not necessary anti-fuzzy ideal as the following example.

Example 4.8.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BZ-algebra. It is easy to show that $I = \{0, 1\}$ and $J = \{0, 2\}$ are ideals of X .

Define a fuzzy subset $\mu, \nu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.3 & x \in \{0, 2\} \\ 0.5 & x \in \{1, 3\} \end{cases}$ and $\nu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.2 & x \in \{0, 1\} \\ 0.4 & x \in \{2, 3\} \end{cases}$. Then μ

and ν are anti-fuzzy Ideals of X . But $\mu \cap \nu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.2 & x \in \{0, 1\} \\ 0.3 & x = 2 \\ 0.4 & x = 3 \end{cases}$ is not anti-fuzzy ideal of X , since $x = 2, y =$

2 and $z = 3$, then

$$\mu \cap \nu(2 * 3) = 0.4 \not\leq \max\{\mu \cap \nu((2 * 2) * 3), \mu \cap \nu(2)\} = 0.3$$

Proposition 4.9.

The intersection of any set of anti-fuzzy ideals of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is also anti-fuzzy ideal of X where is chain (Artinian).

Proof:

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of anti-fuzzy ideals of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, by (AFI₁), we have $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, therefore $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i(0) \leq \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i(x)$.

By (AFI₂), for any $x, y \in X, i \in \Lambda$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y) &= \inf_{i \in \Lambda} (\mu_i(y)) \\ &\leq \inf_{i \in \Lambda} \{\max\{\mu_i(x * y), \mu_i(x)\}\} \\ &\leq \max\{\inf_{i \in \Lambda} (\mu_i(x * y)), \inf_{i \in \Lambda} (\mu_i(x))\} \\ &= \max\{(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y), (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Proposition 4.10.

Every anti-fuzzy ideal of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof:

Since μ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of BZ-algebra X , then by Proposition (4.4), for every $t \in [0,1]$, $L(\mu, t)$ is Ideal of X . By Proposition (2.10), for every $t \in [0,1]$, $L(\mu, t)$ is subalgebra of X . Hence μ is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X by Proposition (3.4). ■

Remark 4.11.

The converse of Proposition (4.10) is not true as the following example:

Example 4.12.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BZ-algebra. It is easy to show that $I = \{0, 3\}$ is subalgebra of X . Define a fuzzy subset $v: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by

$$v(x) = \begin{cases} 0.3 & x \in \{0,3\} \\ 0.8 & x = 1 \\ 0.9 & x = 2 \end{cases}.$$

Then v is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra of X , but v is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X . But it is not an anti-fuzzy ideal since $x = 1, y = 1$ and $z = 2$, then $v(1 * 2) = 0.9 \not\leq \max\{v((1 * 1) * 2), v(1)\} = 0.8$

Corollary 4.13.

If a fuzzy subset μ of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal, then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, $L(\mu, t)$ is an ideal of X .

Proposition 4.14.

Let I be an ideal of an BZ-algebra $(X, *, 0)$, then for any fixed number t in an open interval $(0,1)$, there exist an anti-fuzzy ideal μ of X such that $L(\mu, t) = I$.

Proof:

Define $\mu: X \rightarrow [0: 1]$ by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \in I \\ t & \text{if } x \notin I \end{cases}$. Where t is a fixed number in $(0,1)$.

Clearly, $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$ and we have level sets $L(\mu, 0) = I$ or $L(\mu, t) = X$, which are ideals of X , then from Corollary (4.13),

μ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Theorem 4.15.

A homomorphic pre-image of anti-fuzzy ideal is also an anti-fuzzy ideal.

Proof:

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0)$ be a homomorphism of BZ-algebras, β is an anti-fuzzy ideal of Y and μ the pre-image of β under f , then

$$\beta(f(x)) = \mu(x), \text{ for all } x \in X.$$

Let $x \in X$, then $\mu(0) = \beta(f(0)) \leq \beta(f(x)) = \mu(x)$.

Now, let $x, y \in X$, then

$$\mu(y) = \beta(f(y))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \max\{\beta(f(x) *' f(y)), \beta(f(x))\} \\
&= \max\{\beta(f(x *' y)), \beta(f(x))\} \\
&= \max\{\mu(x *' y), \mu(x)\}. \blacksquare
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.16.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be an epimorphism between BZ-algebras X and Y respectively and f has inf property. For every anti-fuzzy ideal of X , $f(\mu)$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of Y .

Proof:

By Definition (2.15), $\beta(y') = f(\mu)(y') = \inf_{x \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(x)$, for all $y' \in Y$.

We have to prove that $\beta(y') \leq \max\{\beta(x' *' y'), \beta(x')\}$, for all $x', y' \in Y$.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be an epimorphism of BZ-algebras, μ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X with inf property and β the image of μ under f , since μ is anti-fuzzy ideal of X , we have $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

Note that $0 \in f^{-1}(0')$, where $0, 0'$ are the zero of X and Y , respectively.

Thus $\beta(0') = \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(0')} \mu(t) = \beta(x')$, for all $x \in X$, which implies that $\beta(0') \leq \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t) = \beta(x')$, for any $x' \in Y$.

For any $x', y' \in Y$, let $x_0 \in f^{-1}(x')$ and $y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')$ be such that $\mu(x_0 *' y_0) = \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(x' *' y')} \mu(t)$, $\mu(x_0) = \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t)$ and $\mu(y_0) = \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(t)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta(y') &= \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(t) = \mu(y_0) \\
&\leq \max\{\mu(x_0 *' y_0), \mu(x_0)\} \\
&= \max\{\inf_{t \in f^{-1}(x' *' y')} \mu(t), \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t)\} \\
&= \max\{\beta(x' *' y'), \beta(x')\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence β is an anti-fuzzy ideal of Y . \blacksquare

5. Cartesian Product of Anti-fuzzy Ideals

In this section, we discuss the Cartesian product of anti-fuzzy ideals on BZ-algebras and establish some of its properties in detail on the basis of anti-fuzzy ideal.

Definition 5.1 ([9]).

A fuzzy relation R on any set S is a fuzzy subset $R: S \times S \rightarrow [0,1]$.

Definition 5.2 ([9]).

If R is a fuzzy relation on sets S and β is a fuzzy subset of S , then R is a fuzzy relation on β if $R(x, y) \geq \min\{\beta(x), \beta(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Definition 5.3 ([9]).

Let μ and β be fuzzy subsets of a set S . The Cartesian product of μ and β is defined by $(\mu \times \beta)(x, y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \beta(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Lemma 5.4 ([9]).

Let S be a set and μ and β be fuzzy subsets of S . Then

- (1) $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy relation on S ,
- (2) $(\mu \times \beta)_t = \mu_t \times \beta_t$, for all $t \in [0,1]$.

Proposition 5.5.

For a given fuzzy subset β of an BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, let R_β be the fuzzy relation on X . If β is an anti-fuzzy subalgebra R of $X \times X$, then $R_\beta(x, x) \geq R_\beta(0, 0)$, for all $x \in X$.

Proof:

Since R_β is a fuzzy relation of $X \times X$, it follows from that,

$$R_\beta(x, x) \geq \min\{\beta(x), \beta(x)\} \geq \min\{\beta(0), \beta(0)\} = R_\beta(0, 0), \text{ which implies that } R_\beta(x, x) \geq R_\beta(0, 0). \blacksquare$$

Proposition 5.6.

For a given fuzzy subset β of an BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, let R_β be the fuzzy relation on X . If R_β is an anti-fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$, then $\beta(0) \leq \beta(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Proof:

Since R_β is a anti-fuzzy Ideal of $X \times X$, it follows from (AFI_1) ,

$$R_\beta(x, x) \geq R_\beta(0, 0), \text{ where } (0, 0) \text{ is the zero element of } X \times X. \text{ But this means that, } \min\{\beta(x), \beta(x)\} \geq \min\{\beta(0), \beta(0)\} \text{ which implies that } \beta(0) \leq \beta(x). \triangle$$

Remark 5.7 ([9]).

Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ be BZ-algebras, we define (\cdot) on $X \times Y$ by: for all $(x, y), (u, v) \in X \times Y$, $(x, y) \cdot (u, v) = (x *' u, y *' v)$. Then clearly $(X \times Y; \cdot, (0, 0'))$ is an BZ-algebra.

Theorem 5.8.

Let μ and β be an anti-fuzzy ideals of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ respectively, then $\mu \times \beta$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of $X \times Y$.

Proof:

Note first that for every $x_1, y_1 \in X, x_2, y_2 \in Y, (x, y) \in X \times Y$.

$$(\mu \times \beta)(0, 0') = \max\{\mu(0), \beta(0')\} \leq \max\{\mu(x), \beta(y)\} = (\mu \times \beta)((x, y)).$$

Now, let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times Y$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
(\mu \times \beta)(x_2, y_2) &\leq \max \{ \mu(x_2), \beta(y_2) \} \\
&\leq \max \{ \max \{ \mu(x_1 * y_1), \mu(x_1) \}, \max \{ \beta(x_2 * y_2), \beta(x_2) \} \} \\
&= \max \{ \max \{ \mu(x_1 * y_1), \beta(x_2 * y_2) \}, \max \{ \mu(x_1), \beta(x_2) \} \} \\
&= \{ \max \{ \mu \times \beta((x_1 * y_1), (x_2 * y_2)) \}, \mu \times \beta(x_1, x_2) \}
\end{aligned}$$

Hence $(\mu \times \beta)$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$. ■

Theorem 5.9.

Let μ and β be an anti-fuzzy ideals of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ respectively . such that $\mu \times \beta$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of $X \times Y$. Then for all $x \in X, y \in Y$,

- (i) Either $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$ or $\beta(0) \leq \beta(y)$.
- (ii) If $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, then either $\beta(0) \leq \beta(y)$ or $\beta(0) \leq \mu(x)$.
- (iii) If $\beta(0) \leq \beta(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$, then either $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$ or $\mu(0) \leq \beta(y)$.
- (iv) Either μ or β is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X or Y respectively.

Proof.

(i) Suppose that $\mu(0) > \mu(x)$ and $\beta(0) > \beta(y)$, for some $x \in X, y \in Y$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
(\mu \times \beta)((x, y)) &= \max \{ \mu(x), \beta(y) \} \\
&< \max \{ \mu(0), \beta(0) \} = (\mu \times \beta)(0, 0).
\end{aligned}$$

This is a contradiction and we obtain (i).

(ii) Assume that there exist $x \in X, y \in Y$, such that $\beta(0) > \mu(x)$ and $\beta(0) > \beta(y)$. Then $(\mu \times \beta)((0, 0)) =$

$$\max \{ \mu(0), \beta(0) \} = \beta(0)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(\mu \times \beta)(x, y) &= \max \{ \mu(x), \beta(y) \} \\
&< \beta(0) = (\mu \times \beta)(0, 0) \text{ which is a contradiction.}
\end{aligned}$$

Hence (ii) holds.

(iii) It is true by similar method to part (ii).

(iv) Suppose $\beta(0) \leq \beta(y)$ by (i), then from (iii) either $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$ or $\mu(0) \leq \beta(y)$, for all $x \in X, y \in Y$.

If $\mu(0) \leq \beta(y)$, for any $x \in X, y \in Y$, then

$$(\mu \times \beta)(0, y) \leq \max \{ \mu(0), \beta(y) \} = \beta(y).$$

Let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, since $(\mu \times \beta)$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of $X \times Y$, we have

$$(\mu \times \beta)(x_2, y_2) \leq \max \{ (\mu \times \beta)((x_1 * y_1), (x_2 * y_2)), (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, y_2) \} \text{---- (A)}$$

If we take $x_1 = y_1 = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta(x_2) &= (\mu \times \beta)(0, x_2) \\
&\leq \max \{ (\mu \times \beta)(0, (x_2 * y_2)), (\mu \times \beta)(0, y_2) \} \\
&= \max \{ \max \{ \mu(0), \beta(x_2 * y_2) \}, \max \{ \mu(0), \beta(y_2) \} \} \\
&= \max \{ \beta(x_2 * y_2), \beta(y_2) \}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\beta(x_2) \leq \max \{ \beta(x_2 * y_2), \beta(y_2) \}$$

This prove that β is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X .

Now we consider the case $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Suppose that $\mu(0) > \mu(x)$ for some $y \in Y$. then $\beta(0) \leq \beta(y) < \mu(0)$.

Since $\mu(0) \leq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, it follows that $\beta(0) < \mu(x)$ for any $x \in X$.

Hence $(\mu \times \beta)(x, 0) = \max \{ \mu(x), \beta(0) \} = \mu(x)$ taking

$x_2 = y_2 = 0$ in (A), then

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu(y_1) &= (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, 0') \\
&\leq \max \{ (\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * y_1), 0' \}, (\mu \times \beta)(x_1, 0') \} \\
&= \max \{ \max \{ \mu(x_1 * y_1), \beta(0') \}, \max \{ \mu(x_1), \beta(0') \} \} \\
&= \max \{ \mu(x_1 * y_1), \mu(x_1) \}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mu(y_1) \leq \max \{ \mu(x_1 * y_1), \mu(x_1) \}.$$

Which proves that μ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X .

Hence either μ or β is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Proposition 5.10.

Let μ and β be a fuzzy subset of an BZ-algebras $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ respectively . μ and β be anti-fuzzy ideals of X, Y if and only if $\mu \times \beta$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of $X \times Y$.

Proof:

Assume that β is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X . By Proposition (5.7), we get, $\mu \times \beta(0, 0) \leq \mu \times \beta((x, y))$, for any $x, x_1, y_1 \in X, y, x_2, y_2 \in Y$

Let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times Y$, we have from (AFI₂) :

$$\begin{aligned} \mu \times \beta (x_2, y_2) &\leq \max \{ \mu \times \beta ((x_1 * x_2), (y_1 * 'y_2)), \mu \times \beta (x_1, y_1) \} \\ &\leq \max \{ \max \{ \mu (x_1 * x_2), \mu (x_1) \}, \max \{ \beta (y_1 * 'y_2), \beta (y_1) \} \} \\ &\leq \max \{ \max \{ \mu (x_1 * x_2), \beta (y_1 * 'y_2) \}, \max \{ \mu (x_1), \beta (y_1) \} \} \\ &= \max \{ \mu \times \beta ((x_1 * x_2), (y_1 * 'y_2)), \mu \times \beta (x_1, y_1) \} \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mu \times \beta$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of $X \times Y$.

Conversely, suppose that $\mu \times \beta$ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of $X \times Y$, by Proposition (5.8) $\beta(0) \leq \beta(y)$, for all $x \in X, y \in Y$, which prove (AFI₁).

Now, let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times Y$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu \times \beta (x_2, y_2) &\leq \max \{ \mu (x_1 * x_2), \beta (y_1 * 'y_2) \} \\ &= \max \{ \mu \times \beta ((x_1 * x_2), (y_1 * 'y_2)), \mu \times \beta (x_1, y_1) \} \\ &= \max \{ \max \{ \mu (x_1 * x_2), \beta (y_1 * 'y_2) \}, \max \{ \mu (x_1), \beta (y_1) \} \} \end{aligned}$$

In particular if we take $y_1 = y_2 = 0$, then

$$\mu (x_2) \leq \max \{ \mu (x_1 * x_2), \mu (x_1) \}.$$

This proves (AFI₂) and μ is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X .

Hence β is an anti-fuzzy ideal of X by similar method to μ . ■

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